

Impact of hot isostatic pressing on the microstructure of AISI 316L austenitic steel processed by laser direct energy deposition

David Bricín^{a,*}, Zdeněk Jansa^b, Denisa Janová^c, Zbyněk Špirit^a, Petr Beneš^{a,c}, Dana Kubátová^d, Jakub Kotous^e

^a Centrum výzkumu Rez s.r.o., Morseova 1245/6, Pilsen 30100, Czech Republic

^b New Technologies Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Pilsen, Czech Republic

^c Department of Material Science and Technology, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitni 8, Pilsen 301 00, Czech Republic

^d Metrology Laboratory Regional Technological Institute, University of West Bohemia in Pilsen Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Pilsen, Czech Republic

^e COMTES FHT a.s., Prumyslova 995, Dobruška 334 41, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the microstructural analysis of austenitic steel AISI 316L processed by the direct energy deposition (L-DED) process and further processed by hot isostatic pressing (HIP). The samples for the experiment were made from atomised powder with an average spherical particle size of $55 \pm 30 \mu\text{m}$. The powder was processed into blocks with dimensions of $33 \times 33 \times 18 \text{ mm}$, using a deposition layer thickness of 0.6 mm and a Zig-Zag deposition strategy. HIP processing was performed at a temperature of $1150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a pressure of 100 MPa . The analysis of the samples consisted of X-ray phase diffraction analysis and scanning electron microscopy analysis using EDS, EBSD, SE and BSE detectors. X-ray phase analysis revealed that the HIP process causes coarsening of the crystallites size which changed from 26 nm after L-DED to 138 nm after HIP. Microstructural analysis shown that HIP processing led to coarsening of oxide inclusions which size change from $305 \pm 76 \text{ nm}$ for L-DED processed specimen to $342 \pm 88 \text{ nm}$ for HIP processed specimen. EDS analysis shown increase in Si content in the oxide inclusions during L-DED and HIP processing from $1.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ wt. \%}$ to $6.8 \pm 2.0 \text{ wt. \%}$. EBSD analysis shown increase in the HAGB from $56.0 \pm 4.9 \%$ to $81.6 \pm 6.1 \%$ and reduce in LAGB from $13.7 \pm 2.1 \%$ to $1.1 \pm 0.2 \%$ in specimens evaluated Z direction. HIP led to formation of special $\Sigma 3$ grain boundaries. This study confirms that HIP is possible use to tailor microstructure of L-DED processed austenitic steel AISI 316L, which was associated with Ostwald ripening of oxide inclusions and origin of special $\Sigma 3$ high-angle grain boundaries during heat treatment caused by the stress-induced boundary motion.

1. Introduction

Austenitic stainless steel AISI 316L is widely used due to its high strength, ductility, fracture toughness, and corrosion resistance [1]. In the energy sector, it serves for piping, heat exchangers, valves, and pressure vessels, typically up to $\sim 600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [2]. Its long-term stability and corrosion resistance make it particularly suitable for components in the energy and nuclear industry, where long-term integrity is required. Some components can be manufactured or repaired using additive methods (DED, PBF), but broader use in nuclear energy is limited by demanding certification processes [3]. Qualification protocols require a detailed understanding of how AM-specific microstructures and thermal

histories influence long-term mechanical performance and damage tolerance. Before approval, the impact of manufacturing on microstructure and properties must be assessed to ensure long-term service life (40 + years in the case of reactor vessel) with stable mechanical properties and microstructure.

When using the laser direct energy deposition (L-DED) process, AISI 316L steel in powder form is carried by a stream of inert gas to the deposition zone, where a molten pool is created by the simultaneous action of the laser [4]. The movement of the welding head and the building platform then gradually creates the final part, layer by layer. The molten pool formed solidifies quickly due to the high cooling rates (typically $10^3\text{-}10^5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/s}$) associated with the AM process [5]. When

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: david.bricin@cvrez.cz (D. Bricín), zjansa@ntc.zcu.cz (Z. Jansa), janovad@students.zcu.cz (D. Janová), zbynek.spirit@cvrez.cz (Z. Špirit), petr.benes@cvrez.cz, pbenes@fst.zcu.cz (P. Beneš), kubatova@rti.zcu.cz (D. Kubátová), jkotous@comtesfht.cz (J. Kotous).

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additional layers are applied, further temperature cycling occurs, leading to the formation of thermal stresses that manifest themselves and can lead to cracks initiation in the volume of the AM processed parts [6]. Depending on the parameters and deposition strategy and the quality of used powder, various types of pores and defects can be observed in the AM processed part volume such as lack of the fusion pores or gas pores [7]. The microstructure of AISI 316L steel after AM process may be consisted of several minor phases including delta ferrite, oxide inclusions or sigma phase [8]. Their presence depends on the chemical composition of AISI 316L steel and process parameters [9]. Grains morphology of major austenitic phase is then related to the heat flux during deposition process. Typically, it is possible observe zones with coarse columnar grains with size up to millimeters, which related to deposition strategy, and cell substructure [10]. Cells sizes and morphology depend on the thermal gradients and solidification rates in the different areas of melt pool zone during deposition process [11]. These heterogeneities in grain morphology, phase distribution and defect density represent a challenge for certification, because they directly influence fatigue behaviour, stress-corrosion cracking susceptibility and creep performance — parameters crucial for nuclear components. It is therefore evident that during the L-DED process, undesirable phenomena may occur in AISI 316L steel, which may critically contribute to the reduction of its useful properties [12]. This implies that in the case of materials produced by the L-DED process, it is necessary to include post-process strategies after their production that will lead to the elimination of those material defects that contribute most to the deterioration of properties. One such technology is the HIP technology. In the case of critical components used in the nuclear industry, the use of HIP technology for the subsequent processing of materials produced by additive manufacturing technologies appears to be essential, as it is key to ensuring the safety and reliability of the equipment.

Hot isostatic pressing (HIP) after AM processing is applied for microstructure rearrangements and redistribution in acting residual stresses, which both play important role in fatigue and stress corrosion cracking resistance of AM processed austenitic steels [10,13]. Hot isostatic pressing (HIP) belongs to HT processes, which use high temperature (>0.7 melting point) and gas pressure (up to 200 MPa) applied by protective argon or nitrogen atmosphere [10] promoting microstructural transformations. During the process, the pores and defects like short cracks are healed, leading to densification of steel [14]. Moreover, the high heat promotes grain recrystallization, hence, altering mechanical properties of the steel [15]. However, certain cases are described where the high temperature used in the HIP process can cause deterioration of mechanical properties of AISI 316L steel due to grain coarsening [16]. Although HIP is commonly used to remove porosity, its effect on the microstructure and mechanical properties of AM 316L, the risk of grain coarsening, is not fully understood. HIP can additionally influence the dislocation structure, promote recovery, modify the cellular solidification substructure, dissolve minor phases such as δ -ferrite or σ -phase, and alter the fraction of special $\Sigma 3$ grain boundaries, which are relevant for improving cracking resistance. Despite these known effects, the mechanistic relationship between the as-built L-DED microstructure and its transformation during HIP is not yet sufficiently described, particularly in terms of recrystallization behaviour, dissolution of secondary phases, grain boundary character distribution changes, and residual stress redistribution.

In this study, we used HIP to tailor the microstructure of austenitic stainless steel AISI 316L produced by the L-DED process. Microstructure changes associated with HT treatment we described based on the X-ray diffraction analysis and metallography analysis using scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDS) and electron back-scattered diffraction (EBSD). The results obtained from the analyses performed serve to better understand the microstructural phenomena that occur in AISI 316L steel produced by AM technology. The aim of the study is to quantitatively determine how HIP alters the

grain morphology, defect structure, phase composition and grain boundary character of L-DED 316L, and to clarify the mechanisms responsible for these transformations. The results provide insight directly relevant for qualification of AM-produced components intended for long-term operation in the energy sector.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Experimental material and method of processes

AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel in the form of metallic powder was used for producing experimental specimens (builds) with a block shape measuring 33x33x18 mm. The chemical composition of the feedstock was powder was measured with SEM/EDS and compared with the requirements according to the ASTM A240 as listed in Table 1.

Phase analysis revealed that the powder consisted mainly of Fe_3Ni_2 phase, see Fig. 1, with a cubic face centred unit cell (FCC) Fm-3m (ICDD 03-065-5131), lattice parameter $a = 3.600244$ [Å] and a basic cell volume $V = 46.7 \cdot 10^6$ [pm^3]. It was also possible to identify two nickel phases, which differed in their lattice parameter a . The crystallographic data are shown in Table 2. The potential presence of other phases was below the detection limit of the method used.

The feedstock powder was prepared by gas atomisation. Metallographic analysis of the powder revealed that it is composed of near-spherical powder particles with the presence of some satellites on their surfaces, see Fig. 2(a), and the presence of some internal gas pores, see Fig. 2(b), caused by interaction of the powder with the argon atmosphere during atomisation [18]. The presence of these defects and the oxide distribution on their surface, affecting the pore formation and mechanical properties of additively manufactured parts, have been studied by [19,20].

Oxide inclusions were also found in the bodies of the powder particles. These inclusions were mainly Cr-Mn-Si and Mn-Si-rich, due to their affinity to oxygen, and were distributed along the powder particle grain boundaries, see Fig. 2(d-f) with no evidence of their clustering. The size of these inclusions was about 176 ± 53 nm.

Equiaxed grains of the powder particles were randomly spread in their volume with no specific orientation, see Fig. 2(c). Powder particle size distribution, see Fig. 3(a) was compiled based on the image analysis of 1600 powder particles recorded during analysis on scanning electron microscope. The average size of the powder particles was about 55 ± 30 μm , with a main range between 50 and 100 μm , which is in the range for metallic powders (30–150 μm) used for the L-DED process [21]. The powder contained a higher value of particles in the range of 5–50 μm , which could lead to a reduction of powder flowability during the L-DED process due to higher activity of Van der Waals forces between powder particle surfaces [22]. Fig. 3(b), the powder particle shape distribution, shows that 48 % of the measured particles had a circularity higher than 0.8. The presence of satellites and the needle shape of some particles can reduce the circularity of the rest of the powder particles, which also may reduce the powder flowability and may lead to deterioration of the mechanical properties of the specimens.

The feedstock powder was dried prior its processing according to ASTM B213 standard to reduce the moisture and thus to reduce powder particles adhesion and Van der Waals forces [23]. Powder drying was done at 110 °C temperature and holding time 2 h. The feedstock powder was processed using the laser direct energy deposition process (L-DED) with the InssTek MX-600 device in combination with the SDM1600 welding head. The process parameters were selected based on previous experiments with this type of powder and a literature review [18,24,25]. During the L-DED process, the melt pool zone was monitored using two cameras that recorded the printing process and dynamically adjusted the laser power to keep the thickness of the deposited layer stable at 0.6 mm. Average laser power value was around 1000 W. The Zig - Zag strategy was used for specimens builds. Powder dosing amounts and other parameters for powder processing using L-DED are summarised in

Table 1

Chemical composition of AISI 316L powder.

wt%	C	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	S	P	Fe
Requirements (ASTM A240) [17]	< 0.03	16–18	10–14	2–3	< 2	< 0.75	< 0.03	< 0.045	Rest.
Powder (provided by supplier)	0.018	17.6	14.0	2.7	1.5	0.39	0.01	0.01	Rest
Powder EDS	-	18.2 ± 0.3	13.2 ± 0.3	2.9 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.1	-	-	Rest

Fig. 1. Phase composition of AISI316L powder.**Table 2**

Indication of calculated crystallographic data crystallite size and micro strain within the base lattice.

Crystallographic plane	Diffraction angle 2θ [°]	Distance between planes d [Å]	Size of crystallites D [nm]	micro strain $\ast 10^{-3}$ [-]
(111)	50.949	2.079669	61	0.00153

Table 3. The density of the samples after processing using the L-DED process was checked using metallography, by determining the fraction of pores in various directions relative to the printing axis. The average density value after processing was about $99.6 \pm 0.2\%$.

Builds were divided into two groups. One of them was left in “as built” condition and the second one was subjected to heat treatment using hot isostatic pressing (HIP). The HIP process was carried out using the QIH21 HIP unit (Quintus technologies AB, Västerås, SE), and parameters set to 1150 °C for holding temperature, 1 h for holding time, 100 MPa for Argon protective atmosphere pressure, and cooling rate to 6.6 °C/s. The process temperature was chosen because the equilibrium microstructure should consist mainly of the austenite phase [26,27]. It should therefore be suitable for the formation of a recrystallized structure [28]. The second reason for this choice was to increase the efficiency of creep and diffusion processes, which lead to pore elimination and densification of the microstructure during HIP processing [15,29].

2.2. X-ray analysis

X-ray analysis was used to evaluate the phase changes caused by L-DED and HIP processes. All measurements of builds and powder were done on a Bruker Advance D8 powder X-ray diffractometer. Two X-ray tubes were employed for the measurements: a copper X-ray tube and a cobalt X-ray tube. Both were operated in the Bragg–Brentano symmetric geometry configuration. In both cases, diffracted radiation was detected using an Eiger R 500 K detector operating in 1D mode. For materials containing iron, a cobalt tube with a $K\alpha_1$ wavelength of 1.78897 Å is typically used, as this configuration prevents the generation of

Fig. 2. AISI 316 SS steel powder structure. (a) Powder particle surface with satellites; (b) Powder particle cross section; (c) Powder particle IPF map; (d) Etb microstructure of powder; (e) Oxide inclusions at grain boundaries; (f) Oxide inclusions at grain boundaries.

Fig. 3. AISI316L powder properties. (a) Powder particle sizes distribution; (b) Powder particle shape distribution.

Table 3

L-DED process parameters.

Laser power range [W]	750–1050
Beam spot diameter [mm]	1.6
Scanning speed [mm/min]	850
Layer overlap [mm]	0.5
Shielding/dosing gas	Argon
Hatch distance [mm]	1.1
Shielding gas flow [l/min]	10
Dosing gas flow [l/min]	2.5
Powder dosing amount [g/min]	5.6

fluorescence radiation that arises when employing a copper X-ray tube with a $K\alpha_1$ wavelength of 1.540598 Å. However, during the course of the experiment, it was necessary to use a copper X-ray tube. In this case, the discriminator of the Eiger Dectris R 500 K detector was used. By proper adjustment, it effectively suppresses fluorescence radiation, which would otherwise increase the background signal. This effect is clearly reflected in the presented results. The powder sample was placed in a 25 mm diameter diffraction-free circular sample holder. Here the sample was compacted to eliminate the effect of diffraction on the air in the spaces between the powder particles. The irradiated area of the builds by primary radiation was about 15×15 mm. An Eiger 500 K detector was used to detect the diffracted radiation for all types of specimens. The measurement range was chosen from 40° to 98° [20] for the Cu X-ray tube cathode and from 40° to 125° for the Co X-ray tube cathode. The measurements were carried out at a normal temperature of 20°C and atmospheric pressure. All the obtained data were then evaluated by HighScore software and after fitting the diffraction line and deconvolution of the diffraction line, the crystallographic parameters were subsequently calculated. Two libraries of standards were used to determine the measured diffraction maxima and to identify the phases present.

These were the International Centre for Diffraction Data (ICDD) PDF-2 database and the Crystallographic open database (COD). Young's modulus $E = 200$ [GPa] for 20°C and Poisson's constant $\mu = 0.256$ [-] for 20°C were used to calculate the required parameters.

2.3. Metallography analysis

Metallography analysis was carried out on the specimens in the polished state and etched state. The analysis included powder particle surface analyses, powder particle cross section analyses, and build cross section analyses. Powder analysis was done to evaluate particle sizes, shapes, and microstructural composition. The metallography analysis of the builds was done to evaluate the microstructural changes caused by L-DED and HIP processes in the case of grains boundaries and inclusions. A small amount of powder was mounted on double-sided adhesive tape for

morphology and size analysis. The powder was also mixed with PolyFast resin and mounted using a metallographic press for powder particle cross-section analyses. The same type of resin was also used to mount specimens made from both build variants. These specimens were extracted in two directions, one representing the Z direction (L-DED_Z; HIP_Z) of the printing process and the others were extracted in perpendicular direction ((L-DED_Y; HIP_Y). Specimens of powder and builds were ground using SiC grinding foils with a grit size of 220–4000 and polished using MD-Nap polishing cloths in combination with diamond suspensions with particle sizes in the range of 1–3 μm. OPS suspension with a particle size of about 0.25 μm was used as the final step of polishing for EBSD and inclusion analyses. HNO_3 and HCl acids in the ratio 1:3 were used for etching the specimen's structure.

Metallography analysis was done using a Tescan Mira 3 (TESCAN ORSAY HOLDING, a.s., Brno, CZE) scanning electron microscope (SEM) using a SE (secondary electrons) detector, BSE (backscattered electrons) detector, and EBSD (electron backscatter diffraction) detector in combination with local analysis of chemical composition using EDS (Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy). The setup for observation was a view field of 10–1000 μm, a working distance of 9–15 mm, and an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. The specimens for EBSD were pre-tilted by 70° . EBSD was done using a NordlysNano detector with camera set to 8×8 mode with a step size of 0.98 μm and hit rate of about 96–98 % for L-DED and HIP processed specimens. Step size of 0.196 μm was used for powder particle analysis. Step size was set to get minimum 10 pixels/grain as minimum value for detection. Oxford Aztec software (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK) was used to collect EBSD patterns and EDS. The data from EBSD was processed using AztecCrystal software 3.1 (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK) and metallographic image analysis was performed in AxioVision software (Carl Zeiss s.r.o., Prague, CZE).

EBSD analysis was performed approximately in the center of each sample taken, at a minimum of three different locations. Wild spike function and zero solution removal with exclude void's function were used to clean up maps before measurement. Powder particle and oxide inclusions size and shape analysis were both done by image segmentation method using AxioVision software (Carl Zeiss s.r.o., Prague, CZE). At least 15 metallographic images were taken for each of these analyses to quantify the size and shape of the powder particles and oxide inclusions, using Tescan Mira 3 (TESCAN ORSAY HOLDING, a.s., Brno, CZE) scanning electron microscope.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. X-ray analysis

The results of phase analysis of the builds in as L-DED and HIP processed conditions are summarised in Fig. 4. From the data it is possible to conclude that phase composition of builds does not change

Fig. 4. Diffraction analysis of phase composition. (a) L-DED_Y; (b) L-DED_Z; (c) HIP_Y; (d) HIP_Z.

due to HIP treatment, Fig. 4c-d or the L-DED process, Fig. 4a-b. Specimens contained the Fe_3Ni_2 phase similar to the feedstock powder. The presence of other phases was not noted. This implies that the Ni phases detected in the powdered material were transformed into a solid solution of Fe_3Ni_2 during the L-DED process. No other phases were detected. Their possible existence in the sample volume was therefore below the detection limit of the method used.

By comparing the diffraction maxima in the (111) plane, it can be observed that the samples after HIP treatment showed an increase in the diffraction maximum and a significant narrowing of the FWHM (full width at half maximum), see Fig. 5.

This phenomenon is associated with a coarsening of the material structure and an increase in the crystallite size, see Table 4.

For the calculation of residual stress, the in-plane stress tensor method was used. This approach is based on changes in the interplanar spacing (d – interplanar spacing of the diffracting plane, d_0 – interplanar spacing of a stress-free reference) obtained from the measured

diffraction angle θ . The values of θ and d are defined by Bragg's law (Eq. 1):

$$2 \times d \times \sin\theta = \lambda \quad (1)$$

For the calculation of the stress tensor, the tensile Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio μ of the investigated material are also required. The resulting Eq. (2) has the following form:

$$\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 = -\frac{E}{\mu} \times \frac{d - d_0}{d_0} \quad (2)$$

The dislocation density was calculated based on peak deconvolution and extraction of parameters required for the Williamson–Hall (W–H) method. This method was also applied to determine the crystallite size and microstrain within the lattice. Using the measured diffraction angle θ and the full width at half maximum (FWHM), the crystallite size was calculated according to Eq. (3):

$$D = \frac{K \times \lambda}{\beta \times \cos\theta} \quad (3)$$

where K is the shape factor (0.96) and β is the integral breadth. The microstrain was calculated using Eq. (4):

$$\epsilon = \frac{\beta}{4 \times \tan\theta} \quad (4)$$

The dislocation density for a given crystallographic plane was then obtained from Eq. (5):

$$\delta = 1/D^2 \quad (5)$$

where δ is the dislocation density. Based on the W–H method used for determining crystallite size and stress, the uncertainty of crystallite size is $\pm 10\%$, and the uncertainty of the stress value is ± 40 MPa.

The data in the table show that the crystallite size has increased by an order of magnitude compared to the printed samples. The measured and calculated data also show that there was a change in the residual stresses applied in the measured plane. After printing, these stresses were

Fig. 5. Comparison of the shape change of the diffraction line caused by HIP.

Table 4

Indication of calculated crystallographic data crystallite size and micro strain within the base lattice. (111) Crystallographic plane.

Specimen type	Diffraction angle 2θ [°]	Distance between planes d [Å]	Size of crystallites D [nm]	micro strain $\ast 10^{-3}$ [dimensionless]	Residual stresses [MPa]	Dislocation density $\ast 10^{-3}$ [nm ⁻²]
L-DED:Z direction	43.557	2.076171764	26	0.00365	427	0.001523
L-DED:Y direction	43.489	2.079260355	25	0.00367	-735	0.00367
HIP:Z direction	43.483	2.0795	138	0.006801	-838	0.052823
HIP:Y direction	43.5	2.0788	158	0.005916	-547	0.04

disordered, with high tensile and compressive stresses occurring at the surface. In contrast, after HIP processing, only compressive stresses occur in both evaluated directions. Thus, from this perspective, HIP has a positive effect on the development of compressive stresses and homogenisation of the build properties in areas close to the specimen's surface.

The calculated crystallite size in the as-built DED condition is 25–26 nm. When compared with the available literature, see [30–32], it is evident that the measured values fall within the nanocrystalline range typically reported for heavily deformed or surface-modified AISI 316L material.

3.2. Metallographic analysis

Fig. 6a and b shows the structure of the L-DED processed specimens in Y and Z directions. Fig. 6c and d shows the structure of the HIP processed samples also in Y and Z directions. The L-DED structure of the deposited layers consists of columnar and equiaxed grains. The formation of these grains occurs at the interface between the melt and the surroundings and continues into the centre of the melt against the direction of the temperature gradient. The morphology of the resulting grains depends on the correlation between the temperature gradient G , the solidification rate R , and the degree of subcooling ΔT , see [33]. At the boundary of the melt pool, where there is a greater gradient of temperature and cooling rate, the formation of columnar dendrite grains is preferred, while at the centre of the melt pool, where these gradients

are not so pronounced, equiaxed grains are more likely to occur [25].

Heat treatment resulted in the dissolving of the dendritic structure and a change in grain morphology, see Fig. 6(c, d). It is also evident from a comparison of the images that the layering of the material is not evident after HIP treatment. Thus, it can be concluded that the structure of the printed samples has been recrystallised.

EBSD analysis was done for grain structure reconstruction. Fig. 7 shows a comparison of IPF (Inverse Pole Figure) maps for as-built state and HIP treated specimens.

From the data it is possible to observe areas with small grains and elongated columnar grains of austenite phase with epitaxial growth caused by heat transfer during the printing process for the as-built specimens (Fig. 7(a-b)).

Small, recrystallised grains are found in the areas close to the melt interface, while coarser equiaxed grains are found in areas closer to the centre of the melt pool. IPF mapping also shows from a crystallographic point of view that there was preferred orientation in the Z axis with a stronger maximum in $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction for the equiaxed grains, while in the case of fine grains their crystallographic orientation is more random. HIP treatment caused a rearrangement of the grain boundaries, which related to grain polygonization and coarsening of grain sizes, see Fig. 7(c-d) and Table 5.

Grain growth because of HIP processing can be described by the Eqs. 6–7. where D_y ; D_z is the grain size after HIP, D_{y0} ; D_{z0} is the initial grain for evaluated directions Y and Z size after L-DED for evaluated directions Y and Z, k is the kinetic constant, and n is the grain growth exponent.

Fig. 6. Grains structure comparison (a) L-DED_Y; (b) L-DED_Z; (c) HIP_Y; (d) HIP_Z.

Fig. 7. (a) L-DED_Y specimen IPF map; (b) L-DED_Z specimen IPF map; (c) HIP_Y specimen IPF map; (d) HIP_Z specimen IPF map; (e) Low angle grain boundaries distribution (LAGB); (f) High angle grain boundaries distribution (HAGB).

Table 5

Results of grain sizes and grain boundaries comparisons.

Sample	Grain size		Grain boundaries	
	Equivalent Circle Diameter [μm]	Grain size number G	LAGB [%]	HAGB [%]
Powder	3.6 ± 2.7	12.5 ± 0.2	9.7 ± 1.2	50.5 ± 5.1
L-DED_Z	32.1 ± 20.6	6.7 ± 0.5	13.7 ± 2.1	56.0 ± 4.9
L-DED_Y	20.4 ± 14.7	7.5 ± 0.5	12.5 ± 2.3	59.6 ± 4.9
HIP_Z	39.7 ± 31.4	4.6 ± 1.5	1.1 ± 0.2	81.6 ± 6.1
HIP_Y	64.1 ± 61.5	4.2 ± 0.9	1.2 ± 0.3	88.8 ± 5.3

$$d_y^n - d_{y0}^n = d_z^n - d_{z0}^n = k \times t \quad (6)$$

$$n = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{d_y - d_{y0}}{d_z - d_{z0}}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{d_y}{d_z}\right)} \quad (7)$$

The value of the exponent n is a temperature-dependent variable. Its value decreases with increasing temperature [34]. For steels in which no precipitates or defects are indicated, its value is around 2. In the case of a

exponent value around 3, grain growth is influenced by the presence of precipitates in their volume. A value of exponent close to 4 means that the change in grain size is influenced by the presence of a precipitating phase at the grain boundaries. In this case, the coefficient value corresponded to ~ 3.7 . This indicates that grain growth was slowed down during heat treatment by the presence of precipitates in the volume and at the boundaries of austenitic grains.

The orientation of the grains has a similar character to that of the small grains in a printed sample. Grain size was approximately twice as

large for HIP treated specimens as the as-built specimens, see Table 5.

The measured data in Table 6 and Fig. 7(e-f) shows the change in distribution of the proportion between low angle grain boundaries (LAGB) and high angle boundaries (HAGB). This change was associated with substructure rearrangement by LAGB, and formation of twin grain structure in the volume of austenite grains with a disorientation 60° angle (HAGB grain structure).

Fig. 8 shows the grain boundaries with low coincident site lattice (Σ CSL) maps of the samples in the as-built conditions and post-heat treatment states. The average values of $\Sigma 3$, $\Sigma 5$, $\Sigma 7$, and $\Sigma 9$ are shown in Table 6. The data show an approximately two times increase in $\Sigma 3$ boundaries (coherent annealing twins) in particular, which have lower energy than the remaining disordered HAGB. Results from [35,36] show that a higher representation of ordered $\Sigma 3$ boundaries increases the resistance of the material to creep and intergranular corrosion.

Table 6 also shows a comparison of the proportion of these boundaries with samples annealed (SA) at the same temperature in the previous study [37]. From the data, after the HIP process, the structure showed a higher value of the proportion of $\Sigma 3$ boundaries, i.e., the structure after the HIP process should show a higher resistance to the degradation mechanisms mentioned above than the solution annealed structure.

In Table 6 and Fig. 9, the GOS (Grain Orientation Spread) parameter is compared to identify the proportion of the recrystallised grain fraction due to the heat treatment of the samples. The data shows that the HIP treatment resulted in recrystallisation of the structure in almost the entire volume of the analysed regions. The proportion of recrystallised structure was around 95–100 %, which is an increase of about 50 % compared to the printed initial condition. Compared to the samples from the previous study [37], the value of the proportion of the recrystallised structure was about 7 % higher. This implies a positive effect of pressure on achieving a recrystallised structure for the austenitic grains. Compared to the initial powder, the GOS value of the printed samples is then lower, which corresponds to the fact that the grains grow in the direction of heat dissipation from the melt pool area, i.e. they follow the direction of movement of the welding head. The deposition of subsequent layers of material then affects the previously deposited layers thermally, leading to a partial recrystallisation of the structure.

The EBSD phase analysis results (Table 7) showed that the structure of the powder used, and the samples subsequently formed from it, consisted mainly of the austenite phase and contained minor delta ferrite and inclusions. These inclusions differed in their alloying elements and oxygen content.

Particles of complex oxides with elevated manganese, aluminium and silicon contents compared to the surrounding matrix were most observed in the structures of all the samples, see Fig. 10. The cellular structure of the builds showed a difference in chemical composition at the interface and in the centre. The presence of alloying elements chromium and molybdenum was higher at the interface. At the interface between the primary dendritic branches of the printed specimens, the delta ferrite particles were observed, which were again characterised by a higher proportion of molybdenum and chromium relative to their surroundings. After HIP heat treatment, the presence of delta ferrite particles was not evident in the structure of the samples. Various oxide particles were evident in the volume and on the interfaces between

austenitic grains, especially with a higher content of alloying elements, in particular Mn, Al or Mn, Cr or Mn-Cr-Mo, similar as for the raw powder.

The cellular substructure was not evident in the heat-treated samples. This is because the heat treatment was carried out at 1150 °C, whereas the temperature to which this substructure is stable is reported in the literature to be around 800 °C [2]. As the temperature is raised, the cells gradually dissolve, which is associated with dislocation annihilation which accumulates at the cellular structure interface and stabilises it during L-DED build fabrication [38].

By analysing the size of the oxide inclusions in the volume of the samples, the difference in their size between the powder used and the samples further processed by the L-DED process and the HIP process was found. The data shows that the average sub-particle size was around 179 ± 60 nm in the powder, 305 ± 76 nm in the AM samples and 342 ± 88 nm in the HIP treated samples. The difference in the average particle size of the powder is not large, however, the size distribution shows that there is an increase in the proportion of particles with a size of 400 nm due to the HIP process, see Fig. 11(d). In addition to changes in the size of oxide inclusions, a reduction in their amount in the volume of samples after L-DED and HIP was observed. For powder particles, the size of a total of 586 observed inclusions was evaluated, which means an average of 19.5 inclusions per image. for the L-DED processed specimens, there was about 344 inclusions evaluated, i.e., an average of 11.5 inclusions per image, and for the HIP processed specimens, there was about 315 inclusions evaluated, i.e., an average of 10.5 inclusions per image. The process of coarsening of oxide inclusions was associated with a change in their chemical composition see Fig. 11(e). The measured data show a gradual increase in the content of Si in the inclusions volume, while the content of Mn and Cr gradually decreases for inclusions of approximately same sizes, see Fig. 11(e). The change in the distribution of individual elements led to a change in the ratios between Cr/Mn and Mn/Si. The data show that the Cr/Mn ratio gradually increase from 5.2 for inclusions observed in powder particles, through 5.5 for inclusions observed in L-DED samples, to 6.3 for inclusions observed in HIP samples. The opposite trend was observed for the Mn/Si ratio. A value of 4.0 was obtained for inclusions measured in powder particles, a value of 0.7 was obtained for inclusions in L-DED samples, and a value of 0.3 was obtained for inclusions in HIP-treated samples.

Data in Fig. 12 compares the chemistry between oxide particles larger than 1 μm and oxide particles approximately 400 nm in size in a sample after HIP treatment. The data shows that coarser particles have a higher proportion of Mn, Si, and Al elements compared to smaller particles, which have a higher proportion of chromium compared to coarse particles, see Fig. 12(b).

A similar trend can be seen when comparing the chemical composition across the oxide inclusion in the sample after L-DED processing (Fig. 13a) and in the sample after HIP processing (Fig. 13b). The trend shows an increase in the fraction of wt% Si, Mn, and O towards the center of the oxide inclusion. The chemical composition of chromium seems to be similar to that in the matrix for the sample after the L-DED process, while the sample after HIP shows a decrease in its representation towards the center of the oxide inclusion. After HIP processing, a higher fraction of Mn is also evident in the center of the inclusion, while the fractions of other elements remained similar.

Table 6
CSL boundaries and grains orientation spread (GOS) comparison.

Sample	$\Sigma 3$ [%]	$\Sigma 5$ [%]	$\Sigma 7$ [%]	$\Sigma 9$ [%]	GOS [°]	GOS < = 2° [%]
Powder	17.1 ± 3.8	0.9 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 0.9	1.1 ± 1.3	81.3 ± 4.1
L-DED_Z	30.3 ± 8.2	0.9 ± 0.5	0.5 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.5	2.5 ± 1.5	47.4 ± 6.3
L-DED_Y	28.0 ± 4.7	1.4 ± 0.8	0.4 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.5	2.6 ± 1.5	48.0 ± 4.1
HIP_Z	66.4 ± 4.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 4.5	0.6 ± 0.2	98.2 ± 1.4
HIP_Y	66.9 ± 5.8	0.3 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.2	6.6 ± 0.8	0.6 ± 0.2	98.7 ± 1.3
SA	31.9 ± 8.6	0.5 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.2	5.8 ± 2.5	0.8 ± 0.6	91.3 ± 5.4

Fig. 8. CLS maps comparison (a) L-DED_Y; (b) L-DED_Z; (c) HIP_Y; (d) HIP_Z.

When measuring the chemical composition of inclusions, it is important to mention that the EDS method for determining the chemical composition of such fine inclusions is not entirely ideal because, when analysing finer particles, the chemistry of their background, i.e., the matrix, is more reflected in the measurement, which was also evident when comparing the chemistry between coarser and finer particles in Fig. 12, where the presence of Ni and Fe was detected to a greater extent in smaller particles and also its reflected in charts in Fig. 13, where the chromium content decrease in particle is not so evident for L-DED processed specimen.

In terms of shape, the oxide particles were circular in cross section with no apparent segregation in the volume of the prints. The position of the particles in the volume of the printed samples was dependent on the printing strategy, which influenced the Marangoni flow [21]. This flow is dependent on the surface tension gradient of the melt pool during the L-DED process and thus is dependent on the temperature level and temperature gradient in the melt pool. Parameters that affect the flow and thus the position of the particles include, for example, the layer formation rate and the laser energy used [21].

As shown by some simulation calculations of the AM process, laser interaction initiates high temperatures (~ 2862 °C) in the molten pool [39], which can cause the dissolution of the initial oxide inclusions. The size of the newly formed inclusions then depends on the solidification rate, whereby with increasing solidification rate, i.e., cooling rate, which can be up to 10^2 – 10^5 K/s in the case of the L-DED [40], the size of the oxide inclusions decreases [41]. In terms of chemical composition, during the L-DED process, oxide inclusions are preferentially formed, especially based on Mn-Si-O (MnSiO_3), due to the lower Gibbs free energy of Si and Mn and the higher proportion of O in the AM material, which has been confirmed by various studies [41–43] and is in agreement with the results of this work.

Then, during HIP, a change in the size and chemistry of oxide inclusions was observed. It is known from the literature [44] that significant coarsening of inclusions in austenitic steels may occurs at temperatures above 955 °C. The kinetics of coarsening is controlled by Ostwald ripening, which was described by the Lifshitz-Slyozov-Wagner (LSW) theory and can be expressed by the Eqs. 8-11 [44].

$$d^n - d_0^n = k \times t \quad (8)$$

Where: d is the average particle size after heat treatment; d_0 is the initial average particle size; n is particle or grain growth exponent; t is the holding time; and k is the kinetic constant, which can be expressed by the Eq. 9 [44].

$$k = \frac{A \times D \times C_e \times \gamma \times V_m}{R \times T} \quad (9)$$

Where: A is a constant that depends on the particle distribution, D is the diffusion coefficient of the dissolved solute, C_e is the concentration of the dissolved solute in the matrix, γ is the interfacial energy between the particle and the matrix, V_m is the molar volume of the particle's, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature [44].

In Eq. 9, the diffusion coefficient D can be expressed using the Arrhenius equation, see Eq. 10 [44].

$$k = \frac{A \times D_0 \times C_e \times \gamma \times V_m}{R \times T} \times \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{R \times T}\right) \quad (10)$$

Where D_0 is the pre-exponential factor, Q is the activation energy for diffusion

If the equilibrium concentration of dissolved substances does not change with temperature and the parameters C_e and V_m are independent of temperature, then by substituting Eq. 10 into Eq. 8, we can get Eq. 11

Fig. 9. GOS maps comparison (a) L-DED_Y; (b) L-DED_Z; (c) HIP_Y; (d) HIP_Z.

Table 7
Phase fraction comparison.

Sample	Fe-FCC [%]	Fe-BCC [%]	Other phases [%]
Powder	98.0 ± 0.5	1.3 ± 0.5	0.7 ± 0.2
L-DED_Z	97.4 ± 1.5	1.3 ± 0.7	1.5 ± 1.2
L-DED_Y	96.5 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.7
HIP_Z	99.0 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.3
HIP_Y	99.0 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.4

[44].

$$d^n - d_0^n = k_0 \times t \times \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{R \times T}\right) \quad (11)$$

Where: k_0 is the pre-exponential factor of factor k .

The observed increase in the Si content during Ostwald ripening of inclusions caused by HIP treatment is related to silicon's higher affinity to oxygen and diffusivity in austenite compared to Mn and Cr, see Table 8. Accordingly, it was possible to quantify the increasing silicon content in most of the analysed inclusions, regardless of their size. Manganese and chromium, which both have lower diffusivity during HIP processing, migrated from finer inclusions to the metal matrix. Due to the higher diffusivity of Mn compared to Cr, it was possible to observe its increasing mass fraction in the analysed coarser inclusions. Chromium, with the lowest diffusivity, did not have sufficient time to reprecipitate on the coarser oxide inclusions, and thus its mass fraction was lower.

Coarsening of inclusions can occur both by volume diffusion and by diffusion along grain boundaries, which are more active in terms of mass transfer during HIP processing and thus enable rapid Ostwald ripening [26,44].

It is known from the available literature that various types of oxide may form during the processing of austenitic 316L steel using AM technologies. As mentioned above, the most mentioned is amorphous MnSiO_3 oxide, which then disintegrates into a more stable type of crystalline spinel MnCr_2O_4 due to diffusion processes. Inclusions may exhibit a different distribution of elements between the core of the inclusion and its shell [44]. The presence of oxide inclusions, their size, distribution, and chemical composition significantly influence the behaviour and properties of AISI 316L steel after processing.

Cooper et al. [47] report that when the proportion of oxide inclusions exceeds 0.3 vol%, the impact energy drops below 150 J. The authors of the study [42] indicate that AM austenitic steel with a higher occurrence of Si-Mn oxide inclusions and a higher volume of oxygen in the steel matrix exhibits a reduction in impact energy and material resistance to stress corrosion cracking (SCC). Schaller et al. [48] note in their study that, in terms of inclusion size, inclusions measuring several nanometres have no effect on pitting corrosion. Its formation is mainly influenced by larger particles, especially those with a significantly lower chromium content than in the surrounding matrix [43]. Freely dispersed oxide nanoparticles can have a positive effect on the strengthening of the material, its creep properties, and its resistance to radiation damage in case of ODS steels [49,50].

In terms of phases, the samples were mainly composed of a solid solution of Fe_3Ni_2 during processing, with a minor amount of delta ferrite and oxide inclusions. During the L-DED process, the powder melts when it interacts with the laser-melted pool area. Phases and structures continue to form in the sample volume depending on the R and G parameters, which also correspond with the chemical composition of the processed material. Based on the $\text{Cr}_{\text{eq}}/\text{Ni}_{\text{eq}}$ ratio, which is calculated from the amount of alloying elements in the steel (see Eqs. 12 and 13), it is possible to distinguish four variants of structural phase formation

Fig. 10. Examples of EDS analysis areas. (a) Raw powder (b) L-DED cellular substructure; (c) L-DED inclusions; (d) HIP inclusions; (e) Average values of chemical composition for measured points measured by EDS.

Fig. 11. Results of oxide inclusion analysis. (a) BSE image of oxide inclusions of raw powder; (b) BSE image of oxide inclusions of L-DED processed specimen; (c) BSE image of oxide inclusions of HIP processed specimen; (d) Inclusion size distribution diagram; (e) Oxide inclusions with size below 400 nm Cr-Mn-Si content.

from the liquid phase during the L-DED process, see [51,52].

$$Cr_{eq} = Cr + 1.37Mo + 1.5Si + 2Nb + 3Ti \tag{12}$$

$$Ni_{eq} = Ni + 22C + 14.2N + 0.31Mn + Cu \tag{13}$$

$$L \rightarrow L + \delta \rightarrow L + \delta + \gamma \rightarrow \delta + \gamma \rightarrow \gamma \tag{14}$$

Where the values of elements are given in wt%, L denotes melt, δ stands for delta ferrite and γ represents austenite phase

In this study, Cr_{eq} corresponds to a value of 23 and Ni_{eq} corresponds to a value of 14. The ratio between Cr_{eq}/Ni_{eq} is 1.6, which corresponds to the formation of structural phases in the order given in Eq. 14 and is schematically shown in Fig. 14(a).

During cooling, a delta ferrite phase nucleus first forms in the melt

Fig. 12. EDS chemical composition of oxide inclusions and matrix in HIP processed specimen.

Fig. 13. EDS profiles of oxygen (O), silicon (Si), chromium (Cr) and Manganese (Mn) across the oxide inclusion. (a) L-DED; (b) HIP.

Table 8
Diffusion coefficients of Mn, Si and Cr in austenite.

Element	D_0 [m ² /s]	$D_{1150\text{ °C}}$ [m ² /s]	Q [kJ/mol]	Source of Q; D_0
Cr	6.3×10^{-6}	$\sim 7.6 \times 10^{-15}$	243	[45]
Mn	5.5×10^{-6}	$\sim 3.8 \times 10^{-15}$	249.5	[46]
Si	1.7×10^{-4}	$\sim 1.6 \times 10^{-13}$	245.6	[46]

and grows in a uniform dendritic form. During its growth, chromium, nickel, and other elements are redistributed at the interface between the newly formed phase and the melt. As the temperature decreases, a gamma (austenite) phase nucleus forms through a peritectic reaction at the interface between the delta ferrite phase and the melt, gradually replacing the existing phases. Alloying elements concentrate at the interface between the gamma phase and the melt due to their different

solubility in the solid and liquid phases. Cr, Ni, and Mo are more concentrated in the melt near the interface with the solid phase. This segregation of elements then leads to the formation of an austenite cell structure with a higher concentration of Cr and Ni along the boundaries of individual cells, see Fig. 10. With further cooling, the delta ferrite phase decomposes, and the final austenite structure is formed. However, due to the high speeds associated with the L-DED process, a certain proportion of delta ferrite is retained in the structure of the samples, see Fig. 10(c) and 10(e). Its volume fraction can then be estimated based on Nieq and Creq using the Schaeffler diagram, see Fig. 14(b). This shows that the structure of the builds may contain a relatively large percentage of delta ferrite, approximately 9%. This amount is lower, due to the rapid solidification rates of the molten pool associated with the formation of a cellular structure and the formation of other structural phases such as oxide inclusions, which were also observed in the volume of the

Fig. 14. (a) Solidification sequence of material used. Based on ref. [52]; (b) Schaeffler Diagram with marked position of feedstock powder, based on ref. [53].

specimens. These inclusions may be formed by the interaction of the melt with oxygen which was trapped by the melt from the surrounding environment or from the feedstock powder (for example, residual moisture, which also affects the porosity of the specimens). The volume representation of inclusions, distribution and their size then depends on the partial pressure of oxygen, its content [54], amount of deoxidizers (Si, Mn) [9] and the parameters used in the L-DED process [9].

HIP processing led to recrystallisation of the build structure. This was followed by changes in grain boundary arrangement, coarsening of crystallites, grains, and oxide inclusions.

The cellular structure formed during the L-DED process consisted of areas with a higher concentration of alloying elements in the grain boundary areas. Due to the dynamics of the process, dislocations accumulate at the boundaries of the cellular structures, forming dislocation walls and cells and leading to the stabilisation of the cellular structure boundaries. Due to their presence and the presence of delta ferrite at the interfaces between individual cells, there is an increase in the proportion of LAGB in the volume of the samples after the L-DED process. Due to the high temperature and pressure, recrystallisation of the structure occurs, which is associated with plastic deformation of the specimens, creep, and diffusion. Their combined effect causes dislocation movement, which is associated with a change in the position of grain boundaries, and rearrangement, and a reduction in the concentration gradient of Cr and Mo. This is reflected in a reduction in the proportion of LAGB in the sample volume, see Table 5 and Fig. 7. The coarsening of oxide inclusions can then be explained by the Ostwald ripening process, which occurs by the dissolution of small inclusions and the growth of large ones [55]. This process is driven by the tendency of a system to reduce the total free surface energy. Results presented in a study by [49] show that coarsening of oxide inclusions is also affected by grain boundary migration and diffusion through grain boundaries during heat treatment which then lead to coarsening of oxide inclusions at the grain boundaries and in the volume of the recrystallised grains.

The increase in the HAGB value and twins in the sample structures depends on the temperature, annealing time, and pressure to which the samples were exposed during the HIP process. During HIP processing, plastic deformation of the samples occurs in the first phase of the HIP process. This then leads to the formation of dislocations in the volume of the builds. Due to the fact that the pressure acts on the material at an elevated temperature, annealing of the deformed structure occurs at the same time, which then leads to the formation of annealing twins, the number of which increases with increasing temperature, see [56]. As a result of the high-temperature pressure to which the samples were exposed, grain boundaries move in the final stage of HIP processing due to loading. Their movement leads to their gradual annihilation, which is then manifested in a coarser austenite grain structure. The resulting structure after HIP processing is thus created by a combination of dynamic and static recrystallisation of the material structure.

FCC materials with low to medium stacking fault energy (SFE) values typically exhibit preferential formation of annealing twins and CSL $\Sigma 3$ grain boundaries because of thermomechanical processing. These boundaries arise because of the stress-induced boundary motion (SIBM). According to Pande's model, coherent twin boundaries arise from stacking faults on moving grain boundaries. From a crystallographic point of view, annealing twins usually have a planar morphology. It is not typical for a printed structure to form twins in the material structure. Similar to the study by [57], domains referred to as wavy and globular were observed in the structure of the samples after AM processing, which differ in their morphology from the morphology of typical annealing twins and twins formed as a result of plastic deformation. This is due to the process and dynamics of structure formation during AM processing of the material. The authors of the study mentioned above state that the length of $\Sigma 3$ grain boundaries increases with increasing Nieg/Creq ratio with the same AM process settings.

4. Conclusion

This study examined microstructure evolution of austenitic stainless steel AISI 316L processed from raw powder by L-DED process and post-processed by HIP treatment. The impact of L-DED and HIP on grains and oxide inclusions development has been addressed and obtained results can be summarised as follows.

- L-DED process led to formation of columnar and equiaxed grains with cellular substructure which was formed by walls enriched by Cr and Mo and cores with lower content.
- HIP treatment led to suppressing of tensile residual stresses and homogenising of pressure residual stresses in different evaluated areas of builds due to structure densification caused by applied inert gas pressure during the process.
- HIP treatment led to dissolving of cellular substructure which was formed during L-DED process. This related to dislocation annihilation, dissolving of cellular walls, which all led to decrease in LAGB.
- HIP treatment led to grain growth which was associated with the stress induced grain boundary motion and formation of annealing twins and CSL $\Sigma 3$ grain boundaries thus number of HAGB grain boundaries increased.
- L-DED and HIP processes both led to formation of Si-Mn-O rich inclusions. Ostwald ripening of oxide inclusions was possible to observe for builds after HIP process. This phenomenon was associated with increase of Mn and Si content in the inclusions volume with size above 400 nm. Opposite effect was possible to observe for oxide inclusions with size below 400 nm, where content of Cr and Mn continuously decreased. Oxide inclusions growth was also associated with decrease in their number for builds after HIP treatment.

The above results require validation in the future through appropriate technological tests focusing on aspects related to the material's resistance to pitting corrosion, stress corrosion cracking, fatigue, and creep. Some of the experiments also should be focused on the optimization of the HIP process to control the development of grain structure and inclusions, with the aim of obtaining the most comprehensive knowledge about the behaviours and properties of the AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel processed by L-DED and HIP processes, so that in the future it will be possible to integrate them more for component processing in the nuclear energy sector.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Bricín: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Dana Kubátová:** Writing – review & editing. **Jakub Kotous:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Zdeněk Jansa:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Denisa Janová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **špírit Zbyněk:** Writing – review & editing. **Petr Beneš:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors declare there is no use of generative AI.

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none

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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